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Abstract

This document presents the preliminary architecture proposed by the project to advance the state of art in Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) through the introduction of the concept of the Distributed ISAC (DISAC) framework for 6G. The DISAC framework addresses various challenges and proposes innovative enablers designed to support distributed operations enhanced by artificial intelligence (AI) and efficient semantic-native approaches.

Key challenges in transitioning from ISAC to DISAC are identified, including distributed sensing, pragmatic data representation, adaptability to support heterogeneous devices, continuity of sensing services and intelligent resource allocation. Several enablers are proposed to address these challenges.

The document discusses advanced data processing options - such as distributed, hierarchical, and central processing - emphasizing the need for compact data representation to facilitate efficient processing and communication. Architectural challenges related to tracking and handing over passive targets are explored to ensure continuity of sensing services across large areas and extended timeframes.

Additionally, the communication and computation capabilities of diverse devices and the role of sustainable Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS) in enhancing DISAC are examined. The concepts of semantic waveforms and the semantic Radio Access Network (RAN) are introduced, highlighting the benefits of integrating semantic communication into the architecture.

Keywords

6G; Integrated Sensing and Communications (ISAC); Distributed ISAC (DISAC); distributed processing; DISAC architecture; semantic communication; semantic RAN; DISAC enablers;

Disclaimer

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Contents

1	Introduction and challenges.....	10
1.1	Introduction	10
1.2	Challenges	11
1.3	Definition of terms and sensing modes.....	11
1.3.1	Terminology	11
1.3.2	Different sensing modes.....	12
1.4	Document structure	12
2	DISAC architecture enablers	13
2.1	Data processing and data representation	13
2.1.1	Sensing data processing options.....	13
2.1.2	Distributed, hierarchical and central processing	13
2.1.3	Data representation models	14
2.1.4	Architectural challenges	18
2.2	Object tracking and handover support for passive targets	18
2.2.1	Overview	18
2.2.2	Architectural challenges	19
2.3	Support for heterogenous devices.....	20
2.3.1	Overview	20
2.3.2	Communication and computation capabilities of devices.....	21
2.3.3	Control modes and reconfigurability	22
2.3.4	Architectural challenges	23
2.4	Semantic enablers in DISAC	24
2.4.1	Overview	24
2.4.2	Architectural benefits and challenges	27
3	Preliminary DISAC architecture	28
3.1	Architecture design.....	28
3.2	Data processing and data representation in the DISAC architecture	29
3.2.1	Preliminary procedures for data processing and data representation	30
3.3	Object tracking and handover support in the DISAC architecture	30
3.3.1	Preliminary procedures for object tracking and handover of passive targets ...	32
3.4	RIS Integration in the DISAC architecture	33
3.5	The role of the semantics in the preliminary architecture.....	34
3.5.1	Semantic Enabled Sensing Configuration Assistant	34
4	O-RAN deployment options highlighting DISAC architectural features	36

List of Figures

Figure 1 - From ISAC to DISAC.....	10
Figure 2 - Depiction of information fusion.	14
Figure 3 - Different types of data representations.	15
Figure 4 - Pictorial description of target handover.....	19
Figure 5 - Support for heterogeneous devices.	20
Figure 6 - Semantic encoding-decoding for waveforms shaping into DISAC context.	25
Figure 7 - Semantic RAN under ETSI MEC architecture [HEX224-D33].....	26
Figure 8 - Preliminary DISAC architecture.	28
Figure 9 – Example Sensing request sequence flow.	29
Figure 10 - Multi-target tracking and handover pipeline.	32
Figure 11 - Initial RIS integration in DISAC compliant with 3GPP and O-RAN.....	33
Figure 12 - Semantic Enabled Sensing Configuration Assistant.	35
Figure 13 – O-RAN architecture for distributed sensing.....	36
Figure 14 - The 6G-GOALS system architecture [SDS+24].	38

List of Tables

Table 1 DISAC Challenges and Enablers.....	13
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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

3D	Three Dimensional
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
ACK	ACKnowledgement
AF	Application Function
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AoA	Angle of Arrival
BP	Belief-Propagation
BS	Base Station
CFAR	Constant False Alarm Rate
CFR	Channel Frequency Response
CIR	Channel Impulse Response
CNN	Convolutional Neural Networks
CSePF	Central Sensing Processing Function
DBSCAN	Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications
DISAC	Distributed Intelligent Sensing and Communication
DL	Deep Learning
D-MIMO	Distributed MIMO
DU	Distributed Unit
ELAA	Extremely Large Aperture Antennas
FC	Fusion centre
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
FoV	Field of View
IoT	Internet of Things
ISAC	Integrated Sensing and Communication
JCAS	Joint Communication and Sensing
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KVI	Key Value Indicator
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LSePF	Local Sensing Processing Function
Ma-MIMO	Massive MIMO
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
ML	Machine Learning
mMTC	massive Machine-Type Communications
MTT	Multi-Target-Tracking
MUSIC	MULTiple Signal Classification
NEF	Network Exposure Function
NFC	Near-Field Communications

NN	Neural Network
NR	New Radio
O-RAN	Open Radio Access Network
PMBM	Poisson multi-Bernoulli mixture
QoS	Quality of Service
RAD	Range-Angle-Doppler
RAN	Radio Access Network
RF	Radio Frequency
RFS	Random Finite Set
RIS	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces
RU	Radio Unit
SAW	Semantic-aware Adaptive Waveform
SDLA	Semantic Deep Learning Analyzer
SDO	Standards Development Organisation
SeMF	Sensing Management Function
SePF	Sensing Processing Function
SESM	Semantic Edge Slicing Module
SLAM	Simultaneous localization and mapping
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
SRx	Sensing Receiver
SSA	Sensing Service Area
ST	Sensing Target
STx	Sensing Transmitter
ToA	Time of Arrival
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TRP	Transmission Reception Point
UE	User Equipment
VAE	Variational Auto-Encoders
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WP	Work Package
XL-MIMO	eXtremely Large-scale MIMO

1 Introduction and challenges

1.1 Introduction

Despite noteworthy progress in its fundamentals, Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) has often remained at low technology readiness levels (TRLs), presenting various challenges and barriers that need to be overcome before higher levels can be reached. In particular, the current vision for ISAC does not provide support for widely distributed deployments, to track at the same time multiple connected user equipments (UEs) and several passive objects over extended time and space [SAM+25]. The Distributed and Intelligent approach to ISAC (DISAC) framework for 6G brought by the project represents a transformative vision for wireless communications, combining the fusion of heterogeneous and distributed sensors with a highly adaptive and efficient semantic-native approach to enable energy efficient, high-resolution tracking of connected UEs and passive targets as shown in Figure 1. The goal of the DISAC architecture described in current document is to support distributed operations enabled/improved by artificial intelligence (AI), with careful balancing of centralized vs. local data processing supported by fusion of information from different remote sensors and novel multi-antenna technologies.

Figure 1 - From ISAC to DISAC.

Transitioning from centralized sensing to distributed sensing brings both significant benefits and challenges, which can be addressed with strategic approaches. In a centralized sensing setup, a single node is responsible for gathering the sensing data, often resulting in delays in decision-making due to the need to process all data at a central location. This setup also suffers from limited resolution when not all sources are considered, and/or an occlusion issue. Addressing these challenges makes distributed sensing a powerful tool for applications in smart cities, environmental monitoring, and precision agriculture where improved resolution and enhanced reliability over traditional approaches are required.

The 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) network architecture currently offers support for varying communication requirements, including enhanced mobile broad-band, ultra-reliable low latency, and massive machine type communications, as well as the localisation of the UEs. However, significant changes are needed to fully integrate sensing capabilities into it [SAG+24]. 6G-DISAC's goal is to design a network architecture that extends ISAC to imple-

ment the DISAC approach as outlined above in a standards-compliant manner. The main objective of this deliverable is to describe such an architecture and the innovative enablers that make it feasible.

1.2 Challenges

Distributed sensing employs multiple sensing receivers spread across an area, enhancing spatial resolution. This shift in the approach introduces several new challenges which are listed below.

- C1. Finding a parsimonious data representation for distributed processing is a major challenge. Raw sensing data is voluminous and finding the right balance between efficient processing to improve sensing performance for a given service and exchange of sensing data is critical for DISAC. The challenge of choosing a suitable compact data representation is just as important for communication.
- C2. Ensuring the continuity of sensing services over a large area and over time is essential for DISAC. Tracking of mobile passive targets in a seamless manner is necessary to ensure service continuity.
- C3. Allocating resources for sensing and communication in an efficient and intelligent manner is critical to make sure that the overall needs of a DISAC system for different uses are fulfilled.
- C4. Meeting the Key Value Indicator (KVI) and Key Performance Indicator (KPI) objectives listed in [\[6GDISAC-D21\]](#) for DISAC.
- C5. Integrating diverse types of network devices and network elements with varying functionalities and capabilities

1.3 Definition of terms and sensing modes

1.3.1 Terminology

Several of these definitions are taken from [\[3GPP22.137\]](#) and [\[3GPP22.837\]](#).

3GPP sensing data: data derived for sensing purposes from 3GPP radio signals impacted (e.g. reflected, refracted, diffracted) by an object or environment of interest, and optionally processed within the 5G system.

Sensing receiver (SRx): an entity (a New Radio (NR) radio access network (RAN) node or a UE) that receives the sensing signal used by the sensing service in its operation; it may or may not be co-located with a sensing transmitter.

Sensing transmitter (STx): an entity (an NR RAN node or a UE) that sends out the sensing signal used by the sensing service in its operation; it may or may not be co-located with a sensing receiver.

Sensing group: a set of sensing transmitters and sensing receivers whose location is known and whose sensing data can be collected in a coordinated manner.

Sensing service area (SSA): a location area that needs to be sensed with a certain sensing service quality by deriving the characteristics of the environment and/or objects in it from the impacted (e.g. reflected, refracted, diffracted) wireless signals; it includes both indoor and outdoor environments.

Background environment: background (clutter and/or environmental) objects that are not the sensing target(s).

Sensing Management Function (SeMF): the control and management function of ISAC which takes care of receiving sensing requests from services, discovery and selection of sensing nodes (SRx, STx), negotiation of data representations, configuration of sensing nodes.

Sensing Processing Function (SePF): the data processing function for DISAC in charge of collecting measurements from SRxs, processing them based on the negotiated data representation and fusion of data from multiple SRxs (Fusion Centre role).

RIS Controller: the network element, under the network control, which manages the RIS devices in the network.

Autonomous RIS: a RIS device which is not under the network control through the RIS controller.

1.3.2 Different sensing modes

There are different ways to categorize sensing modes that are possible in a network. They have to do with the mapping of the sensing transmitters and receivers to the physical nodes where sensing takes place.

Monostatic sensing: a type of sensing where the STx and the SRx are located on the same device. This facilitates processing, given that STx and SRx may share the same clock (eliminating the need for time and frequency synchronization) and the SRx perfectly knows the transmitted signal. Moreover, since STx and SRx are on the same device, they share the same geometric frame of reference.

Bistatic sensing: a type of sensing where STx and SRx are physically separated from each other. In general, this makes it harder to synchronize STx and SRx. This issue can be overcome by using the line-of-sight path as a reference (in case STx and SRx locations are known) or by using a common external reference signal (e.g. from a beacon). Predetermined pilots by STx and SRx are necessary to ensure accurate estimation. Also, a common geometric frame of reference must be organized between STx and SRx.

Multi-static sensing: a type of sensing that involves several STxs and SRxs and has bistatic sensing as a special case. The same synchronization challenges as the ones associated to bistatic sensing are thus also present. In addition, signals received from various STxs must have a certain level of orthogonality with respect to SRxs configured for measurement on these STxs. In certain types of deployment, it may be necessary to ensure phase coherence between non-localized SRxs. This makes it possible to improve spatial resolution by emulating very large aperture antennas.

3GPP study items make the distinction between UEs and Transmission Reception Points (TRPs) in classifying the modes. According to 3GPP there are six unique sensing modes: TRP-TRP bistatic, TRP monostatic, TRP-UE bistatic, UE-TRP bistatic, UE-UE bistatic, UE monostatic. These may be extended to multi-static modes by adding additional UEs and/or TRPs to the above six basic modes.

1.4 Document structure

In Section 2, the enablers that permit to meet the above challenges are detailed. Section 3 outlines the preliminary DISAC architecture based on these enablers. The final section summarizes the Conclusion and Outlook for future work on architecture in the 6G-DISAC project.

2 DISAC architecture enablers

Four enablers have been identified to tackle the changes described in section 1.2, that are summarized in Table 1 below together with the corresponding challenges each of them is going to address.

Table 1 DISAC Challenges and Enablers.

Enabler	Addresses challenges
Data processing and data representation	C1, C4, C5
Object tracking and handover support for passive targets	C2, C4
Support for heterogenous devices	C3, C4, C5
Semantic reasoning and control	C1, C3, C4, C5

The following sub-sections describe each enabler in detail.

2.1 Data processing and data representation

Sensing applications may need unique and varied service requirements. Sensing nodes participating in providing the sensing services may also have their own limitations in terms of computing power, energy resources and storage capability. This enabler addresses the requirement for intelligent distributed processing and the associated need for adaptive data representation models. This section is structured as follows: first the sensing processing options, are discussed, then an overview of possible data representation models is provided and finally the ensuing architectural challenges are examined.

2.1.1 Sensing data processing options

The classical pipeline for radar detection of objects ([YS+23], [ZL+22]) in the environment performed on the raw data (I/Q samples) obtained as a result of the sensing operation consists of the following high-level steps.

- Detection of peaks in the heat map obtained as a result of signal processing: they indicate potential targets.
- Clutter (objects in the environment, such as buildings, walls, etc.) removal.
- Use clustering to identify and separate targets from each other.
- Apply techniques to deal with extended objects (real-world objects are not points but they have their own shapes and sizes).

2.1.2 Distributed, hierarchical and central processing

Two approaches [LCM+22] at either end of the spectrum with respect to local versus centralised processing are :

Information-Level Fusion: This two-step process involves preliminary detection and estimation of targets at each local sensing node. Local decisions (e.g., detection status) and estimated position-related measurements, such as Angle of Arrival (AoA) and Time of Arrival (ToA), are then transmitted to a fusion centre (FC). The FC performs global detection and localisation through pairing and triangulation of the extracted parameters.

This approach requires relatively low computational power at the FC and low transmission bandwidth between local stations and the FC. However, the performance may degrade due to the simplified extraction of raw data, leading to missed detections or estimation errors at some SRxs.

Signal-Level Fusion: This approach involves directly and jointly processing local raw data from multiple SRxs at the FC for target detection and localisation. By leveraging the full signal information (at the extreme, this could be the I/Q signals sampled at each receiving antenna of each SRx), this method avoids the need for local decision fusion or target-measurement association. This enables optimal processing, as well as a wide range of processing options, offering performance/complexity trade-offs, especially in low Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) scenarios. However, the data volume to be stored and exchanged can be substantial and may pose significant challenges in an ISAC system where communication constraints need to be respected.

It should be emphasized that a variety of other approaches are possible that use and transmit intermediate levels of information, typically processed signals. For example, through channel estimation process, the Channel Impulse Response (CIR) or Channel Frequency Response (CFR) coefficients may be sent to the FC. Another approach involves averaging CIR measurements over time to increase the SNR and reduce the reporting throughput, as shown in Figure 2. The sampled versions of CIR can be transmitted, or a first level of processing can be done: e.g. detect & send the N highest peaks. While channel estimation may be performed at the FC by observing the received pilots, performing the estimation locally at the TRP level may reduce the communication exchange requirements.

Figure 2 - Depiction of information fusion.

The trade-off between the sensing performance and the volume of data to be stored and exchanged represents a major challenge when choosing the approach to be used based on the requirements of the sensing application.

2.1.3 Data representation models

Figure 3 illustrates the sensing data signal processing flow from raw data quantization to progressively higher-level data representations [ZL+22]. From low levels to high levels, data types are listed as quantized raw data, Range-Angle-Doppler (RAD) tensor, point cloud, voxel grids, parametric object, and Deep Learning (DL)-based (or Neural Network (NN)-based) representation.

Figure 3 - Different types of data representations.

In this section, data quantization, radar tensors and point clouds are detailed. Other data representations [YS+23] are also discussed.

Data Quantization

Raw data quantization is the most basic level of data representation and it is crucial in handling large data volumes generated by modern sensing systems, especially in distributed architectures. By reducing the sampled data resolution to a few bits, the communication overhead across a distributed system can be significantly reduced. In extreme cases, one-bit quantization [BB08] minimizes each sample to a single bit, drastically lowering the transmission load. This allows efficient data transfer from local sensing nodes to central processing units, such as from TRPs to the core network, without any need of extensive local data processing.

Advantages and challenges - The primary advantage of using quantized raw data is its ability to reduce data volume, making their transmission more efficient in low-bandwidth, distributed systems. It is straightforward to implement and minimize communication load across the network. However, it poses challenges such as the potential loss of important details, which may require centralized processing for further analysis. Extreme quantization, like one-bit encoding, can also result in degraded quality and precision.

RAD Tensors

Range-Angle and Range-Doppler maps are fundamental data representations in radar signal processing [QW+24], [TJ+23]. In fact, these maps provide a structured way to visualize and analyse the spatial and velocity information of detected targets. In the context of ISAC, these maps are crucial for tasks like target detection, localisation, and tracking. Samples are collected across time, frequency, and antennas, allowing the construction of the RAD tensor. High amplitude values in this tensor indicate the presence of possible targets. The estimation of the targets (i.e., range, radial velocity, direction) can be done using a variety of methods including Constant False Alarm Rate (CFAR) and Multiple Signal Classification (MUSIC).

Advantages and challenges - RAD maps provide a structured and interpretable way to represent spatial and velocity data, making target detection and tracking more efficient by highlighting distinct peaks corresponding to different targets. These maps are essential for accurate

localisation and velocity estimation, and advanced signal processing techniques can be applied to reduce clutter and noise, improving the reliability of target detection. However, RAD maps present challenges due to the large data volume they require to manage, demanding significant computational resources and efficient compression. They are also susceptible to noise, and real-time processing in dynamic, multi-target environments is particularly challenging, necessitating advanced filtering and denoising techniques.

Point Clouds

Point clouds are a versatile and widely used data representation method in various sensing applications, including radar, LiDAR, and computer vision [HC+23]. In the context of ISAC, point clouds provide a spatial representation of multiple targets by capturing discrete points in a three-dimensional space. Each point in the cloud typically contains information about the target's range, velocity, azimuth angle, and elevation angle.

Point clouds can be generated through different methods depending on the sensor type and processing pipeline. In classical radar systems, point clouds are often derived from RAD maps through several steps. First, CFAR detection algorithms identify peaks in the RAD maps, which correspond to potential targets. These peaks are then clustered to form a point cloud, where each point contains attributes like range, velocity, azimuth, and elevation. Alternatively, advanced AI-based techniques can generate point clouds directly from ADC signals[SS+21], using deep learning models to process raw sensor data and extract high-level features, bypassing traditional signal processing steps. This AI-driven approach enhances the accuracy and robustness of target detection and classification.

Advantages and challenges - Point clouds provide detailed spatial awareness, enabling precise localisation and tracking of multiple targets, and are flexible for various applications like object detection, classification, and mapping. They are compatible with ML models like *Point-Net*, enhancing sensing system performance, and can be combined across multiple sensors (e.g., radar, LiDAR, cameras) for improved target detection through sensor fusion. With relatively small data volumes, point clouds are resource efficient. However, they are susceptible to noise and clutter, requiring advanced filtering for improving accuracy. Additionally, point clouds lack inherent object features like shape and size, and pose challenges in object segmentation, often requiring clustering algorithms such as *DBSCAN* or *k-means* to separate multiple objects within a scene.

Voxel Grids

Voxel grids are another form of data representation where the three-dimensional (3D) space is divided into a grid of volumetric pixels (voxels) [LW+18]. Each voxel can store information such as occupancy, intensity, or other attributes. Voxel grids are particularly useful for representing the environment in autonomous driving and robotics applications. They provide a structured representation that can be easily processed by algorithms but it can be memory intensive.

Advantages and challenges – Voxel grids are simple and efficient for representing 3D space uniformly, making them ideal for tasks like spatial discretization, robotics mapping, and input for deep learning models. However, they are memory-intensive, especially for high resolutions, and coarse voxel sizes can lead to detail loss, making it challenging to balance accuracy and computational efficiency.

Deep Learning-Based representations

Recent advancements in deep learning have led to the development of novel data representations [AL+21]. For instance, radar data can be transformed into images or tensors that are

fed into convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for tasks such as object detection and classification. These representations leverage the power of DL to extract high-level features from raw data, improving the accuracy and robustness of the sensing systems. Interesting work has also been done using Variational Auto-Encoders (VAE) which project the input data into a distribution over the latent space. In particular, the following forms of DL representations may be considered:

Embeddings - Typically compressed latent vectors of information that efficiently capture semantic information and relations over the data. Prior distributions and assumptions (such as sparsity or statistical independence) may be exploited to further reduce their size. Typical DL architectures that make use of some form of *embeddings* are VAEs [SV+23], general auto-encoders, sequence transformers, or word embeddings.

Feature vectors (outputs of feature extraction layers) - The first layers of most DL architectures typically identify high-level patterns, which may correspond to the outputs of convolutional layers (that capture specific edges of appearing objects in images) or attention scores (that quantify useful correlations in the input data). *Feature vectors* are conceptually different from the *embeddings* in the sense that they do not necessarily convey interpretable information but are rather intermediate representations that help the overall network learning process.

Layer weights - When the objective of the network is to train edge DL methods (e.g., when federated learning is employed), a common strategy is not to directly transmit data instances (or representations of thereof) to the FC, but rather to perform part of the training locally (at the TRP level) and share some/all of the network's weights periodically with the FC. This methodology can preserve data privacy since one cannot reconstruct the original data inputs from the layer weights.

Advantages and challenges – Deep learning-based representations offer significant advantages, including automatic feature extraction and the ability to manage large and complex datasets, making them highly effective for tasks like 3D object recognition, natural language processing, and computer vision. These models can learn hierarchical patterns, improving accuracy and performance across various applications, such as autonomous vehicles and medical diagnostics. However, they also have notable drawbacks, including high computational costs, a reliance on large labelled datasets, and the "black box" nature that makes it difficult to interpret model decisions, which is problematic in fields requiring transparency, like healthcare.

Parametric object representations

By performing object segmentation over the obtained point clouds, scene information can be conveyed with much less data [PZ+17]. This operation typically involves two steps: (i) clustering algorithms are employed to separate the point cloud into groups that correspond to different objects in the environment; (ii) the points of each group are unified to get a compact representation, therefore unveiling the shape of each object. To describe shapes of 3D objects, multiple approaches may be taken, such as polygon representations (represented as the convex hulls of each point cloud group), wireframes (interconnected sets of edges), or general parametric shapes, where each shape is represented by the set of its geometric parameters (e.g., centre and radius for 3D balls). While accurately representing real objects with geometrical shapes presents its own challenges, once such representation is obtained very few bytes of information need to be transmitted to describe the complete scene.

Advantages and challenges – Parametric object representations offer several advantages, including compactness and efficiency in modelling complex shapes with relatively few parameters. These representations are well-suited for tasks like object recognition, 3D modelling, and simulation, where they can efficiently capture geometric and structural properties. However, there are challenges, particularly when dealing with highly detailed or irregular shapes that are

difficult to capture using fixed parameters. Parametric representations may also struggle with accommodating complex topologies, such as objects with intricate surfaces or varying textures. Furthermore, the process of defining and optimizing parameters can become computationally expensive, especially in real-time applications.

2.1.4 Architectural challenges

The network architecture must support distributed processing across local, edge, and central entities while maintaining the adaptability to meet diverse service requirements. This adaptability enables the system to seamlessly accommodate fully distributed, centralized, or hierarchical processing models. To address the specific sensing needs of a service, the system must determine optimal sensing parameters, data processing methods, and data representations, offering a broad spectrum of flexible options.

However, this high level of adaptability can make the selection process complex. Therefore, the architecture should aim to streamline decision-making by simplifying the negotiation and processes. Additionally, negotiation with potential sensing nodes is necessary to finalize the data representation, ensuring that the chosen representation is compatible with the processing capabilities of the nodes involved. This collaborative approach not only enhances system efficiency but also effectively manages the complexities of data processing and representation while meeting service requirements.

This enabler is particularly relevant to the “VRU protection at a smart intersection” use case defined in [\[6GDISAC-D21\]](#) which involves a large number of devices with varying capabilities at urban intersections. Optimization of both data processing and data representation is necessary to meet the QoS objectives of that use case.

2.2 Object tracking and handover support for passive targets

2.2.1 Overview

Sensors track moving targets via a process known as multi-target-tracking (MTT), which operates after signal sampling and data representation [\[MM+12\]](#). The tracking problem in general involves several key steps: defining suitable target state spaces and their dynamics, choosing a higher-level measurement representation (including uncertainty quantification), operating a state prediction and update (using Kalman filter or similar Bayesian filters). When moving to multiple targets, it also includes estimating the number of targets, target detections (not all targets can be detected with measurements), appearing and disappearing of targets, measurement association (relating measurements to their sources, i.e., either existing or new tracks), and track maintenance (adding, removing, or fusing tracks). MTT can be performed at each sensor or cooperatively among a group of sensors.

To address the aforementioned challenges, researchers have explored various approaches, including geometry-based methods, belief-propagation-based simultaneous localization and mapping (BP-SLAM) techniques [\[EL+19\]](#), and random finite set (RFS) theory-based approaches [\[ZJ+24\]](#). Geometry-based methods are generally favoured for their low computational complexity, making them suitable for resource-constrained scenarios. However, these methods are inherently limited, as they cannot efficiently manage situations with an unknown number of targets or solve the data association problem. BP-SLAM requires ad-hoc adjustments to handle the dynamic nature of landmarks, such as those that appear and disappear over time. Although BP-SLAM methods provide a structured framework, these modifications can become cumbersome. In contrast, RFS-based methods provide a more flexible and comprehensive solution. By modelling landmarks as an RFS, uncertainties regarding both the number of landmarks (cardinality) and the state of each individual landmark can be systematically addressed, thus inherently supporting scenarios with variable numbers of landmarks. RFS-

based methods offer a robust framework for handling data association challenges and managing complex uncertainties, positioning them as a promising choice for advanced MTT systems in dynamic environments. It is also possible to have a list of sensors, which cooperate with each other. In this case, it is possible that all sensors send the measurements to a fusion centre, and the MTT problem is solved using all measurements from all sensors. The methods will be similar to the single-sensor solution, but alternate techniques to solve the data association problem should be considered. Another option is that each sensor does a MTT locally, and then sends the MTT information to a fusion centre, where all MTT results are fused together. Fusion can be achieved using various methods, such as BP-based techniques or by finding a fused posterior that minimizes the weighted Kullback-Leibler divergence of the individual densities.

2.2.2 Architectural challenges

The DISAC framework enables seamless tracking of moving targets across time and space, extending beyond the field of view (FoV) of individual sensors or even groups of bistatic or multi-static sensors. This distributed approach provides two key advantages: First, it ensures target identity maintenance, allowing a target's assigned identity to be consistently recognized across multiple sensors, facilitating smooth target handover. Second, it enables optimized sensing, where sensors can adjust their resource usage (e.g., radio resources, processing complexity, and data representation) based on predicted target movements, even before the target enters their FoVs, enhancing efficiency and accuracy.

However, achieving these benefits requires the network architecture to be designed so as to be able to coordinate sensing activities when multiple sensing nodes are involved as shown in Figure 4. Specifically, the architectural impacts should be considered in the following aspects: coordination between sensing nodes to ensure continuous and smooth target tracking, a uniform notion of target identifiers and data association across sensing nodes, near real-time target prediction and path estimation to ensure that potential sensor candidates for managing handover are warned in a timely manner and are able to adapt their sensing configuration to better track the incoming target. The architectural elements that facilitate these requirements will be detailed later in section 3.3.

Figure 4 - Pictorial description of target handover.

Object tracking and handover is necessary for both use cases defined in the 6G-DISAC deliverable [6GDISAC-D21]. In the smart factory use case, one user story is that of AGV-Human Interaction, where both AGVs and humans are not limited to the FoV of a single or a few BSs in a given part of the factory floor. Proactive path prediction is a necessary element for safety to be guaranteed in this use case story. Thus, this enabler helps to meet the KPIs – “Time to Complete Environmental Mapping” and “Latency in Decision Making” described in section 3.1.5 of [6GDISAC-D21]. Similarly, “VRU protection at a smart intersection” needs extended coverage across different urban intersections and support for path prediction of VRUs in these intersections.

2.3 Support for heterogenous devices

2.3.1 Overview

In integrating communication and sensing into a unified framework through DISAC systems, the need to support heterogeneous devices has become increasingly central, with unavoidable impacts on the architectural design of these networks. As networks evolve, the sheer diversity of devices, ranging from low-power sensors to high-performance user terminals, demands a rethinking of how these networks can effectively manage such a broad spectrum of capabilities, while maintaining stringent requirements for communication and sensing performances.

The motivation for accommodating heterogeneous devices within a distributed ISAC architecture is rooted in the expansive range of 6G applications, such as those detailed in section 3 of [6GDISAC-D21] of this Project. Each of these verticals requires a highly adaptable network, capable of supporting devices with vastly different computational and energy resources, data rates, latency requirements, and sensing precision, as depicted in Figure 5. Failing to account for this heterogeneity risks undermining the versatility that 6G promises to deliver.

From a sensing perspective, the inclusion of different device types, enhances the network’s ability to collect and process environmental data across different domains. The diversity of these devices, each contributing unique sensing modalities and communication patterns, provides a richer dataset for tasks such as localisation, mapping, and situational awareness. However, capitalizing on these benefits demands robust strategies for synchronizing and coordinating devices with vastly differing capabilities.

Figure 5 - Support for heterogeneous devices.

2.3.2 Communication and computation capabilities of devices

2.3.2.1 MIMO and multi-antenna transceivers

Large aperture multi-antenna configurations enable precise beamforming toward desired locations which increases the sensing accuracy, apart from enhancing the communication data rate [LET+14]. This increase in the spatial degrees of freedom, in combination with the large bandwidth of the envisioned systems, additionally paves the way for ISAC-informed waveforms so that both operations can be supported simultaneously without a twofold increase in the respective resource usage [WZD24]. The architecture is designed to support both single antenna and multi antenna components, with their interplay and trade-offs between performance improvements and hardware complexity becoming important topics of investigation within the context of this project. Different versions of MIMO devices may include:

- Massive MIMO (Ma-MIMO) – The next generation of wireless systems is expected to have devices deployed with order of magnitudes larger numbers of antenna elements, to take advantage of numerous degrees of freedom in the spatial domain. Typically, such entities play the role of base-stations where energy, computational, and control requirements may be sufficiently met. Ma-MIMO is designed with multi-user operation in mind, effectively allowing concurrent dual operations of sensing and communication along the spatial domain [LLS+24].
- Distributed MIMO (D-MIMO) – As compared to Ma-MIMO, D-MIMO systems consist of distributed Radio Units (RUs) spread out over the network coverage area and can be used in cell-free systems. D-MIMO networks can improve network metrics by offering a high level of macro-diversity and consistent service quality across the coverage area, by coordinating the distributed RUs [HYM+23]. A cooperative D-MIMO network may contain devices such as fixed and mobile relays to enhance the coverage and service of existing base stations. Distributed devices may have full, limited, or even no access to backhaul. Therefore, an important challenge for D-MIMO is the cost of installing many nodes in different locations that require high-speed Fronthaul (FH) connections.
- Extremely Large Aperture Antennas (ELAA) [WZD24] - Deploying massive antenna arrays with semi-active or even passive beamforming capabilities over prime locations of the environment is posed as one of the key enablers of next generation of sensing-aided systems. The precise beam control offered by the envisioned aperture sizes, in conjunction with higher frequency bands that allow for compact placements of antenna elements offer precise localisation and sensing measurements. Distributed architectures may well employ different sizes of aperture antennas depending on the level of resolution required during each instance of operation. ELAA devices may be deployed as base-stations or they be integrated with emerging technologies such as backscatter communications, cell-free and repeater-based architectures, or RIS-enabled networks [XLJ+24].
- RISs – RIS technology is posed to play the role of one of the key components of future networks, with significant benefits for ISAC. RISs include nearly passive reflection, simultaneous reflection and sensing, and amplifying/transmissive reflection [AP+23]. One of the most important considerations when considering RIS devices in a network is their mode of application, which is primarily mandated by the capabilities of its unit elements. For sensing tasks, RIS technology can be utilised to perform tracking and localisation of both users and passive targets by extracting key channel propagation parameters such as angles, delays, and Doppler shifts, along with geometric data such as the location, orientation, and size of the targets. RIS devices may be non-reconfigurable (i.e., having been designed with fixed reflection patterns to reduce manufacturing costs

[ZML+24]), reconfigurable (i.e., their response can be dynamically adjusted to optimize specific KPIs over time [SCK+24] by the RIS controller exploiting available channel and system information), as well as hybrid RISs, which are RIS devices equipped with local sensing capabilities. Examples include RIS equipped with RF power detectors or (a limited number of) sensors and/or RF chains [ADS+22]. In this case, the RIS controller is physically co-located with the RIS device and autonomously reconfigures its electromagnetic response based on locally available channel state information, as well as a-priori environment knowledge (e.g., the position of base-stations, its own position, etc.) with minimal interaction with the rest of the network.

2.3.2.2 Multi-modal sensors

6G-DISAC focuses on the design of next-generation wireless communication systems. To achieve this goal, a comprehensive architecture integrating sensors with diverse measurement capabilities is proposed. Apart from RF-based sensors and their closely related radar counterparts, multi-modality may be supported by devices such as:

- LiDAR devices predominately equipped on moving user terminals for target detection;
- infrared and thermal detectors for imaging that may operate complementary to various RF-based imaging methodologies;
- camera-bearing edge devices that are specifically designed for local processing, enabling vision-aided communications. Stereo-vision systems with dual cameras may further enable depth estimation alongside RF-based approaches;
- acoustic (predominately ultrasound) sensors that have the capability of providing a new dimension of observed signals from the environment under study.

2.3.3 Control modes and reconfigurability

Notwithstanding the operation of each device, the control of the various distributed components requires special consideration. The envisioned architecture is designed to encompass different levels of control, so that entities requiring constant command as well as autonomous agents may be distributed and cooperate. In practice, the control requirements are heavily linked to the re-configurability of each network device. While the exact description of a device's configuration depends on its nature and functionality, a generic definition is used in this deliverable for re-configuration: a change in some part of the internal state of the device that has an effect on the wireless system, or more specifically, on the sensed signal. The capabilities for reconfigurability are largely mandated by the hardware, computational, storage, and power consumption capabilities. In order to build a comprehensive architecture, it is important to support different levels of reconfigurability and autonomy.

- **Non-reconfigurable:** The first category refers to devices whose configuration, e.g., antenna response, cannot be dynamically adjusted. RISs with static configuration, metallic or metamaterial-based reflectors and absorbers, Near-Field Communication (NFC) or other RFID tags are examples of non-reconfigurable entities that may be used either as part of the core network or as user devices. Upon fabrication or installation, non-reconfigurable nodes may have a pre-disposed behavior that performs a precise and helpful function to the network. For example, fixed antenna configurations or metasurfaces may offer static beamforming for a known set of signal arrival and departure angles. This static approach is evidently limited in terms of performance and achievable functionalities, but no control is needed from the network's side for its operation. Additionally, the manufacturing costs of such devices can be much reduced and depending on the manufacturing technology, they can be implemented to be completely energy passive.

- **Reconfigurable after control:** This is the most typical category for most network devices, whose electromagnetic response or other features can be dynamically adjusted to optimise specific KPIs over time. The internal state of the node is determined by a controller which may be physically collocated with the device or interact with the network over control plane via dedicated control channels. Typical network devices, e.g., base-stations, relays, user-devices, as well as standard RISs, whose operation and control are defined by relevant Standards Developing Organisations (SDOs), fall under this category.
- **Autonomously reconfigurable:** A third category is represented by autonomous devices, which are typically equipped with local sensing capabilities. In such cases, the controller is physically placed at the device to reconfigure its electromagnetic response based on such locally available channel state information, as well as a-priori environment knowledge (e.g., the position of other nodes, its own position, etc.) with minimal interaction with the rest of the network. Examples of such devices may constitute relays, or more crucially, RISs with integrated sensing and computing capabilities that can be deployed for autonomous operation.

2.3.4 Architectural challenges

Architectural challenges posed by such heterogeneity are significant, due to the different operation modes, control requirements, and synchronisation of all considered devices. In fact, distributed ISAC systems must not only balance the quality of service (QoS) demands of devices with differing data throughput, latency, and reliability needs, but also ensure efficient resource allocation across the network. Ensuring that even the most resource-constrained devices can benefit from the enhanced communication and sensing capabilities of 6G, without introducing inefficiencies, remains a critical challenge for system designers.

Despite the exact choice of sensors, which is motivated by the deployment scenario and use-case, the sensing procedures can be comprehensively captured by the architecture presented below in this deliverable. In fact, data processing and representation procedures previously illustrated are general enough to support different data modalities as well as concurrent multi-modal sensing schemes. For instance, if devices are limited in terms of computation but less so in terms of communication, they could opt to do minimum local processing and send the raw data for sensing signals for upstream processing.

As highlighted in sections 2.3.2 and 2.3.3 control and configuration is of paramount importance in DISAC for heterogenous devices in general and distributed antenna systems in particular due to their impact on network performance. Devices of type “Reconfigurable after control” (section 2.3.3), need a controller which interacts with the network to modify the device configuration. This includes optimization of the device configuration for the selected KPIs, which may be related to specific communication or sensing functions or addressing DISAC metrics. Autonomously reconfigurable devices have little interaction with the network from the control perspective. However, when they have local sensing capability, they may be considered as SRxs. The ability of the architecture to provide proper control mechanisms for all the considered distributed antenna technologies is critical to ensure the coverage extension and increased SNR performance for both sensing and communication over the extended areas, as well as enabling advanced sensing applications.

2.3.4.1 In-band and out-of-band control

The deployment of distributed devices, alongside its increased benefits, brings new challenges in terms of control, coordination, and synchronization. Therefore, the DISAC architecture highlights the importance of the control plane as one of its main pillars. However, the minimization of control signalling is of paramount importance when devising the DISAC approach. To that

end, current architecture proposal is designed to support devices that require sparse control signal, or even autonomous nodes that interact with the network without explicit control. At the same time, the in-band channel is envisioned to be part of the control link, by developing pertinent waveforms and deploying devices that decode control messages alongside the communication packets or sensing signals.

2.3.4.2 *Storage, computational hardware, and offloading*

The distributed operation of numerous devices calls for the development of a simultaneous computational capability design over the network. While the functional description of the architecture makes no assumption on the physical location of the sensing processing and control blocks, distributed network devices co-located with those computational and data-collecting nodes are supported. From this perspective, the architecture supports devices with varying computational capabilities, equipped with diverse computing and storage hardware. For the devices that have large capabilities, such as base stations, RUs with continuous power consumption, or autonomous RISs, a full sensing processing function can be co-located with the radio device. Since different levels of computational capabilities need to be supported, the corresponding devices are assumed to be equipped with different types of computational hardware. This may include embedded hardware for low-capacity computations, to full central processing units and hardware accelerators capable of performing ML tasks at the edge of the network. Mechanisms for offloading computation and storage should be implemented to allow limited-capability hardware to delegate these tasks to edge modules that are better equipped to manage them.

2.4 Semantic enablers in DISAC

2.4.1 Overview

The design of traditional communication systems aims to maximize data transmission rate with minimal errors, focusing purely on bit-level accuracy. However, this is typically achieved by introducing information redundancy and/or increasing link budget and diversity, thus increasing the use of resources. In some cases, and especially when the application/intent of communication is known at the transmitter and the receiver, this overshoot of resources might not be necessary. To achieve this, the emerging semantic communication framework represents a paradigm shift by introducing meaning (semantics) and intent (goal-orientation) into the communication process. This framework proposes to prioritize the transmission of the most relevant and meaningful information for a specific task, rather than the exchange of data without context [SB21]. Semantic and goal-oriented communications, by focusing on the meaning of the transmitted information rather than simply the quantity and the quality of the data, have the potential of improving network efficiency, reducing bandwidth usage, and addressing the increasing demand for high-speed data transmission.

The proposed Distributed-Intelligent-ISAC paradigm envisions the optimization of large-scale and distributed communication provisioning with location and context information available from distributed processing [SAG+24]. Data retrieved from multi-modal sensors, integrated within the wireless network infrastructure, can lead to high resolution sensing, but at the cost of large amount of information that need to be processed. In this context, semantic reasoning enables reducing data volume over time and space through intelligent processing and AI-based reasoning. The introduction of the semantic and goal-oriented concept in the ISAC framework enables not only the semantic extraction, but also the fusion of the data derived from different sensing modalities, by leveraging the composition of semantically selected information. In the DISAC context, the semantic framework provides further advantages in terms of interoperability, contextual understanding, and effectiveness in activating sensing functions [SAM+25]. This includes context and application-adapted waveform design, signal processing,

intelligent resource allocation, robust protocols as well as reasoning about multi-modal sensed information.

2.4.1.1 Semantic waveforms

6G-DISAC aims to optimize the performance of ISAC systems by employing optimised and flexible waveforms, shaped to consider several transmitters and receivers, several connected UEs and (passive) objects, and several frequency bands. The project is exploring AI/ML semantic-aware solutions to provide localisation, sensing, communication and control target task-level performance, while allowing intelligent and parsimonious resource exploitation (in terms of spectrum, energy, time, etc.). The semantic transceiver includes also revisiting waveforms optimization, channel parameter estimation, location estimation and tracking, to adapt to instantaneous application requirements. In the context of WP3 of the 6G-DISAC project, a Semantic-aware Adaptive Waveform (SAW) for communication is currently being studied (Figure 6). Here, the waveform shaping computation is based on an orthogonal basis decomposing a waveform under sequential forms, leveraging the Walsh transform and the associated modulation and combination of the Walsh coefficients.

Figure 6 - Semantic encoding-decoding for waveforms shaping into DISAC context.

From the architectural perspective, the control and configuration of SAW need to be addressed. Further issues such as the coexistence with traditional OFDM waveforms, the provisioning of the knowledge base(s), the configuration of the parameters and the models updating, will be investigated during 6G-DISAC project.

2.4.1.2 Sematic RAN

The connection between the semantic and the radio domains is envisioned as the exchange of semantic information between different network functionalities, which implies the introduction of new protocols and network functions, including semantic extraction, semantic composition and semantic instruction. The DISAC network architecture should enable the support of AI modules at both semantic and radio layers, while specific interfaces need to be designed to enable interactions of these new functionalities. As an example of possible integration in existing designs, in the context of the Hexa-X-II project, the concept of a semantic RAN based on the ETSI MEC architecture is proposed, in [HEX224-D33] (Figure 7). Here, different components are integrated in the existing architecture. They show how the new proposed functional blocks SDLA and SESM can be enabled by the ETSI MEC. Specifically, with the integration of the SDLA, the ETSI MEC can obtain the task requirements and calculate the task

latency and accuracy functions. The SESM, with this calculated latency and accuracy functions, processes the requirements of the task and calculates the optimal offloading policy, the compression level, and the computation and radio slicing.

Figure 7 - Semantic RAN under ETSI MEC architecture [HEX224-D33]

2.4.1.3 Semantic alignment in the ISAC context

Semantic alignment refers to the process of ensuring that both the transmitter and the receiver share a common understanding of the transmitted information. Incorporating semantic alignment into the ISAC (or JCAS) framework represents a significant advancement for 6G, IoT, and autonomous systems [ZGZ+24]. In the context of ISAC, semantic alignment involves aligning the meaning of sensed data and communicated information to enable more efficient use of resources and reduce misunderstandings between these systems. In terms of architecture, the semantic alignment of ISAC requires to introduce several changes to the design and operation of traditional communication and sensing systems:

- joint semantic encoder for communication and sensing, to optimise the trade-off between communication and sensing competing for shared resources;
- semantic-aware resource allocation module, to dynamically adapt network resources to the current semantic context;
- semantic decoder, to interpret the received semantic information and generate outputs aligned with the original goals of both communication and sensing tasks;
- shared knowledge base and contextual model between communication and sensing subsystems, to enable meaning alignment and adaptation to an evolving context.

Akin to the DL-based representations described in section 2.1, semantic-based representations for sensing will be investigated during the project.

2.4.2 Architectural benefits and challenges

Semantic and goal-oriented communications present several benefits in terms of architectural design. Specifically, in the DISAC context by transmitting only the semantically relevant information, the architecture can significantly reduce the huge amount of data, retrieved from a dense sensor deployment, that needs to be transmitted. This is especially beneficial for massive IoT networks or low-power devices, as in the envisioned DISAC environment. Since the system transmits only goal-relevant information, the overall transmission time is reduced, leading to lower latency, which is crucial in mission-critical applications like the Vulnerable Road User protection at a smart intersection use case, explained in deliverable [\[6GDISAC-D21\]](#). Semantic processing can enable more efficient use of network resources, such as spectrum, bandwidth, time and computational power; this is especially important for 6G networks, where energy efficiency and resource optimization are key design goals, as envisioned for the DISAC framework to allow intelligent and parsimonious sensing and communication. Contextual and intelligent communication can also ensure that decisions and actions are based on the actual meaning of the transmitted data, leading to smarter, more autonomous systems and then to a more robust and reliable sensing. Furthermore, as more devices and sensors get connected, semantic communication allows the architecture to scale more efficiently, avoiding data overload by focusing on meaningful communication.

However, the several benefits we could gain from using the semantic and goal-oriented communication technology present numerous challenges. To fully leverage the semantic framework, there is the need for a cross-layer coordination, enabling the seamless flow of the semantic information between different layers. Many applications, such as localization and sensing, autonomous systems, sensor deployment in smart factories, can benefit from edge computing to process semantic data at the edge of the network, reducing the burden on central servers and ensuring lower latency. AI/ML models running on edge devices can handle real-time semantic extraction and compression of data collected from distributed sensors. A semantic-aware control plane could be introduced to manage contextual knowledge sharing across the network. This control plane ensures that all nodes involved in the communication process (e.g., mobile devices, IoT sensors, edge servers) maintain a synchronized knowledge base to facilitate semantic alignment. A resource orchestrator become essential for resource management, ensuring that the required QoS and QoE is met. In the architectural design, there is the need for an effective resource allocation and orchestration mechanisms that operate even when incomplete or partial context awareness is available.

3 Preliminary DISAC architecture

The preliminary DISAC architecture presented here builds upon the ISAC chapter of the deliverable D3.3 of the SNS-JU project Hexa-X-II [HEX224-D33], which is extended here by addressing the challenges based on the new enablers defined in section 2 (see Table 1). [HEX224-D33] englobes the sensing control and processing into a single entity named SeMF which is in the network core (centralised solution). In the DISAC architecture, there is a clear separation of the control and processing network functions, support for local/edge and central sensing processing, enablement of target tracking and handover, and support for distributed antenna technologies.

The work presented here should be considered as preliminary as not all aspects covered in DISAC will be developed or integrated in this version. The distributed processing and seamless handover of passive targets has been investigated in fair amount of detail. The RIS aspects of “support for heterogenous devices” has been partly described while other aspects such as resource allocation for communication-assisted sensing will be treated in the final version of this deliverable. The same goes for studying the architectural implications of sensing-assisted communication.

3.1 Architecture design

Figure 8 below illustrates the preliminary DISAC architecture.

Figure 8 - Preliminary DISAC architecture.

The Sensing Management Function (SeMF) receives sensing service requests from a sensing application which is typically an Application Function(AF) but can be a UE or a Network Function(NF). The SeMF is responsible for the discovery, selection and configuration of the sensing nodes (STx and SRx, RIS, etc.) in the sensing service area. The Sensing Processing Function (SePF) takes care of processing the sensing measurements for tasks like target detection, localisation, and tracking.

The Network Exposure Function (NEF) is a core functionality in 5G that securely exposes network services to an Application Function (AF), as depicted in the example sequence flow Figure 9 the full list of terms and their definitions are available in the Terminology subsection 1.3.1).

It should be noted that this process involves negotiation between candidate sensing nodes and the SeMF. Certain nodes (such as UEs) could opt out of participation due to constraints such as energy. The SeMF may also deem that certain devices do not meet the requirements needed to fulfil the sensing services.

In the following subsections the relationships between the architectural elements and the enablers are described and the challenges described in section 1.2 addressed by the proposed architecture are highlighted.

Figure 9 – Example Sensing request sequence flow.

3.2 Data processing and data representation in the DISAC architecture

The SeMF, after having selected the sensing nodes, proceeds to a negotiation of data processing and the data representation that will be used for serving the sensing request. The choice depends on the service requirements and on the sensing devices available in the sensing service area. As detailed in the section 2.1, a variety of possibilities is available in terms of where data processing is done and the type of data to be exchanged between the SRxs and the SePF.

In the SotA, the SePF is either central or at the network edge [LZJ+23]. A major innovation in the proposed architecture is a fully distributed SePF. The signal processing needed for sensing could be performed locally at the SRxs by a Local Sensing Processing Function (LSePF), at the edge of the network or at the central SePF, as illustrated in Figure 8.

As noted in section 2.1.2, signal level fusion offers optimum sensing gain. The architecture allows SRxs to send full signal information to a centralized SePF (CSePF) or edge SePF. At the other extreme it is also possible for an SRx to use LSePF to perform sensing signal processing completely locally and send a high-level measurement report to the SePF. Of course,

a variety of intermediate options are also possible with processing occurring at the local, edge and central levels. In all cases, the fusion is done at the edge or central SePF.

The negotiation of the selection of the data representations by the SeMF and the fully distributed SePF addresses challenge C1 "finding a parsimonious data representation for distributed processing". It also helps in addressing challenge C4 "meeting the KVI and KPI objectives for DISAC" as the service requestor and the SeMF will ensure a data representation that fulfils the service requirements is used. Finally, it is also a facilitator for challenge C5 "integration of diverse types of network devices and network elements" as in the sensing node selection process the capabilities of the devices are taken into account.

3.2.1 Preliminary procedures for data processing and data representation

The discovery of the capabilities of the sensing nodes and their configuration enables the system to determine the appropriate data representation for transmitting sensing reports, as depicted in Figure 9. This capacity to discover node capabilities also allows the sensing system to support heterogeneous devices by adapting to the constraints of specific devices.

The procedure may be described as follows.

1. A sensing request is received by the SeMF from an Application Function with the service requirements and a Sensing Service Area (SSA).
2. The SeMF, based on the knowledge of the network elements in the SSA, selects potential candidates to participate in the sensing service. The selection criteria include the sensing service requirements and the knowledge of the position and capacity of the fixed sensing nodes¹ such as BSs and RISs. The selected candidates need to confirm their participation to this sensing request. They also indicate their capabilities².
3. In DISAC, a group of sensing nodes are needed to perform the requested sensing service over the SSA. (they will share common sensing configuration including the data representation³). The SeMF chooses this data representation based on the sensing service requirements. The SeMF creates a group (could be the same or a subset of the above selected candidates) and configures the nodes with shared sensing configuration, the data representation to be used, the refresh rates.
4. The sensing service can now be started and with the participation of LSePF and SePF: sensing measurements are performed and sensing reports are received by the SePF.
5. SePF performs the fusion of the sensing reports and sends the result via the SeMF and the NEF back to the AF.

3.3 Object tracking and handover support in the DISAC architecture

Seamlessly tracking multiple mobile targets over a large area and over extended time periods is another major innovation in the architecture. As introduced in section 2.2.2, this involves several architectural challenges and extensions. Figure 10 illustrates the different steps involved in this process.

¹ Mobile nodes such as UEs could also participate in the process (not treated in this preliminary procedure description).

² The ability to perform local processing i.e. act as a LSePF, is part of the capabilities.

³ The manner in which service requirement KPIs are matched with data representations is still under study.

- **Coordination between sensing nodes** - A key aspect of the DISAC architecture is the coordination between sensing nodes to ensure continuous and smooth target tracking. Coordination is crucial for real-time target handover, as multiple sensors need to cooperate to track targets as they move between their FoVs. The Sensing Management Function (SeMF) plays a key role in this coordination activity.
- **Target identifiers and data association** - To ensure consistency across the network, target identifiers must be uniformly recognized across all participating sensing nodes. Data association, or matching sensor measurements to the correct target track, also needs to be handled, ensuring that all sensors are tracking the same target in a consistent manner. This data association is essential for the handover process, as it guarantees that each node understands that it is receiving the same target from another sensor. In a centralized approach, the SeMF assigns unique target IDs and communicates this information to all relevant nodes that have the target within their FoV. Data association is also handled at the SeMF in collaboration with the SePF.
- **Target prediction and path estimation** - Target handover relies heavily on accurate target path prediction. Sensing nodes must be able to predict when a target will leave their FoV and which new sensing nodes are expected to detect the target next. This prediction may need to be localized to minimize latency, allowing sensing nodes to make real-time decisions on their own while still communicating essential updates to the SeMF. For many of the sensing use cases, the prediction can be done at the SeMF. The SeMF may also maintain a global map of targets and predicted paths (similar to Simultaneous Localization and Mapping, SLAM), which would help improving prediction accuracy and handover decisions. The global map could serve as a reference for maintaining up-to-date tracking information across all nodes in the system.
- **Sensing configuration adaptation** - The SeMF can instruct sensing nodes to adjust their own sensing configurations based on incoming target information and the maintained global map. For instance, if a target is predicted to enter a new SRx's FoV, that sensor may modify its sensing configuration (e.g., increasing its resolution or adjusting its radio resource allocation) to ensure effective target detection and tracking. This dynamic adaptation of sensing configurations ensures that sensing nodes are always prepared for upcoming targets, optimising resource management and improving detection accuracy.

Figure 10 - Multi-target tracking and handover pipeline.

Addressing the above challenges will ensure smooth tracking of targets and coordination of nodes. This architectural extension addresses challenge C2 “ensuring the continuity of sensing services over a large area and over time”. It also helps with C4 “meeting the KVI and KPI objectives for DISAC” (for instance, it improves the coverage of the sensing service and thus the KVI of the Geographical Inclusiveness).

For future implementations, the global map could become dynamic, such that it is updated and maintained by the SeMF as needed. This would allow the SeMF to have a complete overview of the environment and improve its ability to manage the network's sensing resources and track coordination. Additionally, exposure of this global map, or elements thereof, via the Network Exposure Function (NEF) to authorized Application Functions (AF) needs to be studied.

3.3.1 Preliminary procedures for object tracking and handover of passive targets

Based on the architectural considerations described in section 2.2.2 , the target handover procedures are summarized as follows:

1. Target selection and ID assignment: when a new target, which has been selected to be tracked, enters a sensor's FoV, the SeMF assigns a unique target ID and returns it to the sensing nodes, ensuring the target is consistently tracked across the system.
2. Handover preparation and alerting: the local SePF or central SePF reports the predicted target's movement to the SeMF; if the target is likely to leave the SRx's FoV based on predicted measurement, the SeMF makes a choice to notify the relevant SRxs that the target is approaching their FoV, allowing the new SRxs to adjust their sensing configurations and optimize their resource allocation.
3. Sensing node coordination and data exchange: sensing nodes exchange data with the SePF during the handover process to maintain the target's identity tracking and position; the SePF ensures consistent data association across nodes to form a unified track.

As noted in section 2.3, for sensing tasks some RIS device types can extract key channel propagation parameters such as angles, delays, and Doppler shifts, along with geometric data such as the location, orientation, and size of the targets. Such RIS supports the LSePF function to perform the above parameter extraction and communicates these sensing measurements to either the Local/Edge or the Central SePF.

This architecture helps meet challenges C4 “meeting the KVI and KPI objectives for DISAC” by a) extending the coverage for sensing services and b) improving energy efficiency as in the absence of the RISs, SRxs may need to use more energy to detect targets. It also enables to meet challenge C3 “efficient and intelligent allocation of resources for sensing and communication” as the role of the RIS allows the network to dedicate less resources for sensing. Finally, it helps partially with challenge C5 “integration of diverse types of network devices and network elements of varying functionalities and capabilities” by allowing low capacity SRxs (such as some UEs) to offload the computation to the RIS.

3.5 The role of the semantics in the preliminary architecture

Section 2.4 has provided an overview of the role of semantics in DISAC and also outlined a few potential enablers.

The impact of Semantic-aware Adaptive Waveform (SAW) is primarily one of provisioning of AI modules, models and configuration that are needed. The semantic RAN enabler also needs such provisioning. This topic is already well treated in the literature for example in [[HEX224-D33](#)]. Some other aspects of semantic RAN are dealt with in the context of O-RAN in section 4.1.2.

Complementary to the work done in section 3.2, a semantic component designed to assist with data processing and data representation has been investigated. This component also relates to the semantic RAN in the ISAC context and is described below.

3.5.1 Semantic Enabled Sensing Configuration Assistant

In section 2.1.4, the need to simplify the process of choosing appropriate sensing parameters, data processing methods and data representations for sensing services has been highlighted. The Semantic Enabled Sensing Configuration Assistant illustrated in Figure 12, is a component that interfaces with both the sensing service and the network to provide such a facilitating service.

Figure 12 - Semantic Enabled Sensing Configuration Assistant.

It receives the service objectives from the sensing service and context information from the network and the sensing service. The context information will include information such as the SSA, the position and capabilities of sensing nodes in the SSA, knowledge on antenna deployment (type, number, and position) and other relevant information that are useful for this selection process. This process is closely related with the procedures detailed in section 3.2.1 on data processing and data representation. The goal is to assist the SeMF in both the selection of the sensing nodes that participate in the sensing service and the sensing configuration to be used for the same.

4 O-RAN deployment options highlighting DISAC architectural features

This section presents a deployment model of the proposed DISAC architecture, aligned with the Open-RAN (O-RAN) paradigm guidelines. It highlights how distributed processing, as described in the DISAC framework, can be effectively integrated within the O-RAN architecture. Additionally, the section explores considerations for building a semantic framework on top of the hierarchical O-RAN architecture, enhancing its capabilities for intelligent sensing and communication.

4.1.1 Distributed processing in O-RAN

The O-RAN-based architecture aims to design and build mobile networks that emphasize openness, interoperability, and flexibility. Specifically, the O-RAN deployment is built upon the following key-pillars:

- **open interfaces:** O-RAN uses open interfaces between different network components, allowing for greater flexibility and choice in selecting vendors and technologies, which is in contrast with traditional (monolithic) network paradigm where vendors tightly control their equipment and interfaces;
- **virtualization:** O-RAN leverages virtualization technologies to run network functions on standard hardware, making it easier to deploy and manage network services, with advantages in terms of greater flexibility in scaling and capability to adapt to changing network demands;
- **cloud-native architecture:** O-RAN embraces cloud-native principles, enabling the deployment of network functions in the cloud, with benefits like scalability, agility, and cost-effectiveness;
- **interoperability:** O-RAN promotes interoperability between different vendors' equipment, allowing operators to mix and match components from different suppliers. This increases competition and drives down costs.

Figure 13 – O-RAN architecture for distributed sensing.

Figure 13 shows how O-RAN deployment can support distributed sensing and communication architecture. In this configuration the target, i.e. the dog, could be sensed by the neighbouring UE and also by the nearby radio units (RUs) in the area.

The distributed unit (DU) is responsible to handles the lower layers of the protocol stack, which includes the Upper Physical, MAC, and RLC layers. Moreover, in distributed sensing configuration, the DU could handle also local sensing processing function (LSePF) such us extracting sensing features from RU measurements, (e.g. Doppler, periodogram, time averaging, etc). These target features could also be forwarded to a central SePF for further processing and data fusion.

The signals reflected by the target/object and measured by the UE could also be reported directly to the sensing processing function (SePF) for further dedicated processing. The SePF performs high level processing such as point cloud fusion, object position/speed/orientation estimation, object classification, etc.

4.1.2 The O-RAN-based semantic architecture

The semantic framework can be built on top of the hierarchical O-RAN architecture, where the semantic plane leverages a semantic controller and semantic orchestration. In the context of the Hexa-X-II project, the deliverable on architectural enablers [[HEX224-D33](#)] outlines the concept of a semantic RAN which allows for efficient allocation of resources and processing based on the O-RAN architecture. In the spirit of collaboration between SNS projects, the ongoing work on Semantic O-RAN in the SNS project 6G-GOALS which is focused on AI-empowered architecture to support semantic and goal-oriented communication protocols and services [[SDS+24](#)] will be followed. As can be seen in Figure 14, the 6G-GOALS proposed system architecture introduces two key components. The first is an intelligent controller acting at the envisioned semantic plane level to enable a programmable and extensible platform for the deployment of semantic-oriented applications. The second is an engine acting at the orchestration level to manage the semantic information resource processing, the lifecycle of semantic modules, and the user experience. There is potential for Communication Aided Sensing and Sensing Aided Communication in this context. Developing this kind of semantic architecture on O-RAN, include enhanced compression and resilience, allowing efficiently processing of vast amount of data. The knowledge-driven semantic awareness can provide target task-oriented performance with reduced resources and transmitted data. The native AI applications can enable distributed sensing and localisation, as well as large-scale deployment capabilities. The inclusion of intelligent network functions could enable highly robust and very wide-band ISAC with increased spectrum and power efficiency, together with an enhanced local processing, compression, and sharing of information. Leveraging an O-RAN based semantic architecture could finally also provide a holistic vision of the multiple targets in an environment of interest and their characteristics.

However, new semantic interfaces need to be specified to facilitate the exchange of information and metrics between the application plane and the semantic controller, which provides intelligent and programmable platforms for the deployment of semantic applications. The controller needs specific interfaces to be connected to both control and user plane and it is envisioned to be directly connected to an upper-level entity, responsible for the effective and efficient delivery of semantic-oriented services through the orchestration of semantic resource processing and user experience management.

Figure 14 - The 6G-GOALS system architecture [SDS+24].

5 Conclusions and outlook

This deliverable outlines the challenges that must be addressed for a distributed and intelligent Integrated Sensing and Communication (DISAC) system. It describes the necessary enablers to overcome these challenges and presents a preliminary proposal for DISAC architecture that incorporates these enablers. In particular, the document provides extensive details on the enablers related to "Data Processing and Data Representation" and "Object Tracking and Hand-over Support for Passive Objects".

These enablers introduce significant innovations to the current state-of-the-art architecture for distributed sensing. The support for fully distributed sensing processing, which enables intelligent signal processing locally at the device, at the edge or within the network core, offers substantial benefits in accommodating a wide range of service requirements. Furthermore, the capability for intelligent tracking of passive targets across large areas and extended timeframes is essential for ensuring the continuity of sensing services, representing a significant advancement in improving the TRL of current ISAC solutions.

The topic of "Support for Heterogenous Devices" encompasses a diverse range of devices. This document outlines some architectural challenges associated with RIS. The effective and intelligent management of the control and configuration of various RIS devices is crucial for facilitating the deployment of DISAC solutions in real-world scenarios. Additional aspects such as other distributed antenna technologies and computation/communication constraints of devices, will be further explored in Work Package 4, and will be elaborated upon in the final version of the 6G-DISAC network architecture proposal.

Finally, the concepts of semantics in DISAC have been outlined and an overview of the broad scope of potential semantic enablers has been presented. An in-depth exploration of a multi-faceted semantic architecture is not the primary focus of the 6G-DISAC project. Nevertheless, further studies will be conducted later in the project as part of Work Package 3. Additionally, the ongoing work on Semantic O-RAN within the SNS project 6G-GOALS will be monitored, and its impact on the proposed architecture will be assessed.

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